

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF REFLEXIVE SKILLS IN TEACHER TRAINING

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Abstract

The article examines the theoretical and practical importance of the formation of reflexive skills in teacher training. Reflexive activity plays an important role in the analysis, evaluation and development of a teacher's own professional activity. During the study, the positive impact of developing reflective thinking skills of future teachers on the quality of pedagogical activity was determined. Also, the ways of applying reflection methods in teacher training and their role in the pedagogical process were explained. Reflexive activity allows the teacher to identify his strengths and weaknesses, make pedagogical decisions in accordance with the individual characteristics of students, and make the learning process person-oriented.

Keywords: reflection, teacher training, reflexive activity, pedagogical skills, education.

Reflective portfolios are an important tool in teacher training because they allow students to document the problems they encounter in the teaching process, analyze their experiences, and use the results they obtain as a basis for future action. This process not only develops teachers' critical thinking skills, but also supports them in making creative pedagogical decisions and solving situational problems. One of the theoretical foundations of reflective practice was put forward by Donald Schön (1983). Schön describes reflection as an integral and important component of professional activity, and at the same time understands it as "the professional reflective person evaluates and reinterprets his or her activity by considering the sequence of his or her experience." This approach shows that reflective activity is not only a tool for analysis for a teacher, but also a key resource in the formation and implementation of professional decisions. Schön's theory serves as a theoretical basis for planning teacher development strategies in modern pedagogical practice[4].

In addition, scientific research conducted in recent years has shown that reflective activity directly affects the development of teachers' professional skills. Research has shown that reflective thinking allows teachers to effectively prepare lesson plans, select teaching methods according to the situation, and increase students' learning achievements [3]. Reflective skills allow teachers not only to evaluate what is happening in the lesson, but also to plan the future teaching process on a more purposeful and scientific basis.

At the same time, reflective activity creates conditions for the teacher to systematically record, analyze, and draw conclusions from their own experience. Using a reflective approach, teachers identify failures and problems they encounter in the teaching process, try alternative solutions, and enrich their experience for future activities. This approach serves both the teacher's self-development and the improvement of the quality of the teaching process in the educational institution.

The modern education system requires the teacher not only to be a person who transmits knowledge, but also to act as a professional who constantly evaluates, analyzes, and develops his or her own activities. In this regard, reflective skills are considered one of the main

components of teacher training. Reflection is an important tool for a teacher to critically approach his/her own activities, identify successes and shortcomings, and improve his/her future activities.

Globalization and the development of innovative technologies have necessitated the introduction of new approaches in the education system. These changes require teachers to have creative thinking, problem-solving, and self-analysis skills. The formation of reflective skills of future teachers ensures their professional development and increases the quality of teaching.

Reflective activity helps a teacher to objectively evaluate his/her own pedagogical activities, identify problems that arise in the learning process, and find ways to solve them. Therefore, the development of reflective skills in higher pedagogical education institutions is of particular importance.

Thus, reflective activity serves not only as a key mechanism for the teacher's personal development, but also as a key mechanism for strategic decision-making and increasing pedagogical efficiency in the educational process. Modern pedagogical research shows that the formation of reflective skills in teacher training strengthens the integration of theoretical knowledge into practice, encourages teachers to think creatively and analytically in their professional activities, and ultimately leads to an increase in the educational achievements of learners [3;5].

Reflective skills act as a key tool in the formation of an effective connection between knowledge and practice in teacher training. These skills allow a teacher to apply not only theoretical knowledge not only to imitate, but also to apply them in practice, thus making pedagogical decision-making and teaching process management more purposeful and effective.

In particular, reflective skills provide the teacher with the following opportunities:

1. Improving pedagogical decision-making: The teacher critically evaluates the decisions made and the methods applied during the lesson through a reflective approach. This evaluation process is not limited to detecting errors, but also serves to further develop and optimize the application of successful strategies in the

teaching process. As a result, teachers become more creative, flexible and adaptive in the teaching process.

2. Personality-oriented pedagogical approach: Reflective skills allow the teacher to adapt lesson plans and management strategies to the individual characteristics of students. By thinking reflexively, the teacher takes into account the knowledge level, motivation and learning style of students, thus teaching activities are carried out in accordance with both individual and collective goals. This approach not only increases the quality of education, but also strengthens teacher-student relationships.

3. Continuous professional development: Reflective activity allows the teacher to analyze situations that arise in the teaching process and plan his future activities more purposefully. Based on experience, the teacher identifies his strengths and weaknesses, analyzes the difficulties he encounters, and develops strategies to overcome them. This approach, in addition to ensuring the professional development of the teacher, also brings continuous innovation and improvement to his pedagogical activity [3].

International studies show that the attention paid to reflective activity during the internship strengthens the effective integration of theoretical knowledge into practice in teacher training. For example, as emphasized in the scientific articles entitled “Reflection in Teacher Education”, studies conducted on students’ reflective portfolios have shown that their reflective levels increase over time, that they think deeply, and that they systematically evaluate their pedagogical experience [2].

Thus, the development of reflective skills is of strategic importance in teacher training in terms of both strengthening theoretical knowledge and forming practical skills. Reflective activity encourages teachers to think more objectively, evaluate the teaching process, and plan their future activities purposefully. This, in turn, has a direct impact on improving the quality of education and the continuous development of the teaching profession.

Reflective activity is multifaceted and makes significant contributions to the professional development of teachers in various aspects. This activity is not limited to the acquisition of knowledge, but also serves to form the teacher's experience-based decision-making skills, critical thinking and continuous professional development.

1. Self-analysis: One of the main components of reflective activity is the systematic analysis of the teacher's own experience. This process allows the teacher to identify his strengths and weaknesses, assess his professional skills and make plans for future activities. Through self-analysis, the teacher evaluates the results achieved in the teaching process, examines the effectiveness of the methods used in the lesson and develops strategies appropriate to the situations arising in practice. This approach directly affects not only the teacher's self-development, but also the quality of the teaching process. [2].

2. Critical thinking: Reflective activity allows the teacher to objectively and analytically assess the difficulties, problems and unexpected situations encountered in the teaching process. This allows the teacher

not only to identify problems, but also to develop alternative solutions. Critical thinking involves the teacher in the decision-making process appropriate to the situation and helps to adjust lesson plans to the individual needs of students. At the same time, the teacher evaluates the shortcomings and successes that arise during teaching and builds his pedagogical activity in a more purposeful and strategic way. [4].

3. Professional development: Reflective thinking acts as a mechanism that ensures the continuous professional development of the teacher. By reflexively analyzing his experience, the teacher prepares plans for future activities, tries out new pedagogical strategies and improves his methodological skills. Reflective activity also allows the teacher to update teaching practices, organize the learning process more efficiently and apply innovative approaches in education. This serves to form the teacher's professional identity and continuously optimize his activities.

Thus, these three main aspects of reflective practice—self-analysis, critical thinking, and professional development—interact with each other in teacher preparation. has an impact. The teacher is not only satisfied with possessing theoretical knowledge, but also learns to apply this knowledge in practice, analyze the teaching process and develop his/her own activities. This approach significantly increases both the teacher's professional skills and the quality of teaching. [2;3].

Various organizational and practical measures are being implemented in the field of teacher education in Azerbaijan to develop reflexive activity. These measures do not limit teachers to acquiring only theoretical knowledge, but also create conditions for them to systematically analyze and improve their professional experience. For example, seminars and webinars held within the framework of the “Reflexive Teacher” project implemented by the Institute of Education are important platforms aimed at developing teachers' reflexive activity.

In these trainings, teachers analyze their lesson plans, the pedagogical methods they use and the assessment criteria through reflexive questions. The analysis process is not limited to assessing the current situation; teachers also identify the difficulties that arise in the teaching process, consider alternative solutions and plan their future activities more purposefully. Thus, reflective questions enable teachers to develop an analytical and creative view of the teaching process.

At the same time, these workshops improve teachers’ skills in approaching the lesson from different pedagogical perspectives. Teachers learn to evaluate the teaching process not only from one side, but also from the perspective of the individual needs of students and the strategic goals of teaching. This develops their critical and creative thinking skills in the pedagogical decision-making process.

This promotion of reflective activity allows teachers to document and systematically analyze their practical experience. Teachers use the results obtained within the framework of seminars and webinars in the preparation of future lesson plans, record the lessons learned in their portfolios, and continuously optimize their pedagogical activity. As a result, reflective activ-

ity not only ensures the personal professional development of teachers, but also serves to improve the quality of teaching and the application of innovative methods in the educational process.

This approach also strengthens teachers' skills in creative decision-making and situational problem-solving in the educational environment. Teachers analyze various pedagogical scenarios through seminars and webinars, discuss their experiences with other colleagues, and ultimately make reflective thinking an integral part of practical activity. Thus, the promotion of reflective activity in the Azerbaijani teacher education system directly contributes to both the development of teachers' professional skills and the improvement of students' learning achievements.

Reflective portfolios act as an integral component of teacher training and provide students with the opportunity to analyze their experiences systematically and in writing. Portfolios do not only serve the purpose of documenting teaching activities; they enable teachers to reflexively evaluate their own activities, identify successes and challenges. This process is critical for teachers to review practical experience and develop strategies for future activities.

The application of reflective portfolios helps teachers integrate theoretical knowledge into practice. Through the portfolio, teachers analyze the pedagogical methods used in each lesson, students' learning outcomes, and assessment criteria. This allows the teacher not only to improve his/her lesson plan, but also to objectively and structuredly assess the problems he/she encounters in the teaching process. Thus, portfolios act as a fundamental tool for both teacher self-development and pedagogical decision-making.

Portfolios also reflect the social and professional aspects of reflection. By sharing the experiences recorded in the portfolio with colleagues in both individual analysis and professional settings, the teacher enriches the pedagogical experience and contributes to the formation of a collective reflective environment. This approach shows that reflective activity is not only important for the personal development of the teacher, but also in terms of systematizing professional experience, sharing pedagogical experience and improving the quality of the educational environment.

In addition, reflective portfolios help to develop teachers' critical thinking and analytical skills. While systematically recording teaching experience, the teacher analyzes the cause-effect relationships of his/her decisions, evaluates alternative strategies and creates a basis for new approaches to be applied in future lessons. This process allows the teacher to integrate professional reflection into daily practice, and as a result, the teacher ensures the transformation of theoretical knowledge into practice in teacher training [2;4].

Thus, reflective portfolios play a role of a bridge between practice and theoretical knowledge in teacher training, allowing the teacher to objectively evaluate his/her own performance, develop continuous development strategies and improve pedagogical decision-making. This approach significantly increases both the professional skills of the teacher and the quality of teaching and emphasizes the role of reflective activity in both the personal and professional environment.

Reflective activity is considered a key and integral component of continuous professional development in the field of education. This process gives the teacher not only the ability to apply theoretical knowledge, but also the opportunity to systematically and critically evaluate his/her own practical activity, draw lessons from the results obtained and plan his/her future activity in a more purposeful and strategic way. Thus, reflective activity strengthens the teacher's professional decision-making process, ensures the evaluation of his/her performance from the prism of critical thinking and supports the formation of a professional personality [4].

Modern research shows that teachers involved in reflective practice approach the teaching process with a broader and more multifaceted pedagogical perspective. They conduct assessments not only by considering specific problems that arise during the lesson, but also by considering the individual needs of students, learning styles, and the dynamics of the learning environment. Such teachers objectively analyze the lesson process, identify successes and weaknesses, and ultimately develop strategic plans and pedagogical interventions to improve learning outcomes [2].

Reflective activity also strengthens teachers' continuous professional learning and development skills. By reflexively evaluating their own experience, the teacher tests new pedagogical methods, optimizes teaching plans, and integrates lessons learned from experience into future activities. This approach directly affects not only the teacher's personal development, but also the quality of teaching and the improvement of students' learning achievements.

At the same time, reflective activity allows teachers to develop critical and analytical thinking skills. The teacher analyzes problems that arise during the lesson, evaluates cause-and-effect relationships, and considers alternative solutions. This allows the teacher to be more purposeful and creative in pedagogical decision-making. As a result, reflexive activity, along with the development of the teacher's professional identity, also increases the skills of situational problem solving, adaptive approach and strategic planning in the teaching process.

Thus, reflexive activity acts as the main support for teacher training and continuous professional development in the field of education. It allows the teacher not only to criticize teaching activities, but also to develop the skills of learning from experience, optimizing pedagogical decisions and purposefully planning their future activities. This not only increases the professional skills and quality of teaching of teachers, but also directly contributes to improving the learning achievements of students [2;4].

The conducted research shows that the formation of reflexive skills in teacher training has a significant impact on the effectiveness of the professional activities of future teachers. Reflection allows teachers to analyze their activities, identify their mistakes and improve the quality of the pedagogical process.

In the modern educational environment, reflexive thinking is considered one of the main indicators of the professional competencies of a teacher. Therefore, the application of methods and tools aimed at the develop-

ment of reflexive activity in higher education institutions is important. Discussions, practical exercises, self-assessment and pedagogical practices in the training process have a positive effect on the formation of reflexive skills.

It can be concluded that the development of reflexive skills increases the quality of teachers' professional training and allows them to achieve successful results in their future activities.

References

1. Aghayev A. Training process and modern pedagogical technologies. Baku: Education, 2018, 256 p.
2. Bayramov A., Alizade A. Psychology. Baku: Maarif, 2017, 620 p.
3. Javadov I. Psychological foundations of pedagogical activity. Baku: Chasioğlu, 2018, 240 p.
4. Alizade A. Pedagogical foundations of teacher training. Baku: Elm, 2014, 276 p.
5. Kazimov N. Issues of pedagogical mastery. Baku: Maarif, 2016, 214 p.
6. Guliyev S. Modern pedagogical approaches and teacher competencies. Baku: Education, 2021, 205 p.
7. Mehdiyev R. Teacher training in the modern education system. Baku: Science and Education, 2020, 198 p.
8. Veysova Z. Active/interactive learning. Baku: Institute of Educational Problems, 2015, 184 p.